

NITROGUARD, AN INNOVATIVE BIOFERTILIZER PAINT FOR TREE TRUNKS USING *AZOTOBACTER CHROOCOCCUM* (NITROGEN FIXING BACTERIA)

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Article Received on 03 Feb. 2026,
Article Revised on 25 Feb. 2026,
Article Published on 01 March 2026,
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18885625>

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How to cite this Article: Krishnaveni R.*¹, Ayesha Shafeeka M.¹, Eugin Amala V.³, Dharani K.⁴, Hasin Riha H.⁵, Sathiyapriya S.⁶, Sakthi Janani R. M.⁷ (2026). Nitroguard, An Innovative Biofertilizer Paint For Tree Trunks Using *Azotobacter Chroococcum* (Nitrogen Fixing Bacteria). *World Journal of Pharmacy and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 15(3), 1012–1021.

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ABSTRACT

Excessive use of chemical nitrogen fertilizers has caused serious environmental and soil health problems, especially in long-term tree cropping systems. To provide a sustainable alternative, this study developed **NitroGuard**, an innovative biofertilizer paint formulated with the free-living nitrogen-fixing bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* for application on tree trunks. The water-based formulation, prepared using slaked lime, casein, and glycerol, maintained viable bacterial cells ($\approx 10^8$ CFU/mL) for 48–72 hours after application. The bacteria colonized bark microcrevices and gradually migrated to the rhizosphere, contributing to biological nitrogen fixation and the release of plant growth-promoting substances. Field trials on mango, guava, and neem trees showed improved leaf greenness, shoot growth, and overall vigor compared to untreated controls. NitroGuard offers a low-cost, eco-friendly alternative to chemical fertilizers for tree crops.

KEYWORDS: *Azotobacter chroococcum*, Biofertilizer paint, Biological nitrogen fixation, Tree trunk inoculation, Plant growth–promoting bacteria, Sustainable agriculture.

INTRODUCTION

Tree crops are vulnerable to soil nutrient depletion, especially nitrogen. Traditional fertilizers are costly and environmentally unsustainable. To overcome this, we propose **NitroGuard**, an eco-friendly biofertilizer paint containing *Azotobacterchroococcum* — a free-living nitrogen fixer. NitroGuard is a water-based, eco-friendly trunk paint carrying viable cells of *Azotobacterchroococcum*, a free-living nitrogen-fixing bacterium. When brushed onto tree bark, the formulation maintains microbial viability during the first 48–72 hours, enabling colonization of bark microcrevices and subsequent movement to the rhizosphere via runoff, or passive entry into surface tissues through lenticels. *Azotobacter* contributes modest but continuous biological nitrogen input and secretes plant-growth–promoting metabolites (IAA, vitamins, siderophores). The paint also provides sunscald protection and minor wound sealing. The pilot targets fruit and timber trees (e.g., mango, citrus, guava, neem, ficus).

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Soil organisms play a pivotal role in shaping the environment through their contributions to soil formation, nutrient cycling, stimulation of plant growth, and the detoxification of both organic and inorganic pollutants. Specific microbial species inhabiting the rhizosphere, the region surrounding plant roots, have a profound impact on ecosystem development, plant vitality, and even weather monitoring. These rhizospheric microbes rely on carbon sources found in root exudates and plant litter.(**Sharma, D et al., 2025**).

Soil parameters, such as temperature, moisture, aeration, and nutrient composition, significantly affect plant growth and development. Agricultural methods currently depend on chemical fertilizers and pesticides to increase crop yields. However, excessive use of these fertilizers may lead to environmental pollution, soil deterioration, and the accumulation of heavy metals. These beneficial microorganisms, including bacteria, fungi, and algae, can improve soil fertility, stimulate plant development, and increase nutrient uptake.(**Monica, S et al., 2025**).

The thin layer of soil (about 1 to 2mm thick) surrounding crop roots and the volume of soil occupied by roots are known as the rhizosphere. Plant growth results from interaction of roots and shoots with the environment. (**Chakraborty, A.P., 2020**).

Nitrogen fixation is mainly responsible for improvement of crop yield. In this regard, diazotrophs like *Rhizobium*, *Azotobacter* and *Azospirillum* are important as they enrich nitrogen nutrition in N-deficient soils. Of these, *Azotobacter* promotes plant growth as well as nitrogen fixation. Thus technology has been developed for making use of *Azotobacter* biofertilizer for nitrogen and non nitrogen fixing plants (Sethi, S.K. and Adhikary, S.P., 2012).

The continuous decline of earth's natural resources and increased use of harmful chemical fertilizers pose a great threat to the health of soil. Exploitation of microbes as biofertilizers are considered to some extent an alternative of chemical fertilizers. They have extensive potentiality in enhancing crop production, food safety and maintaining long-term soil fertility which is essential for meeting global food demand. Microbial fertilizers are not only cost-effective, nontoxic and eco-friendly but also serve a good substitute for expensive and harmful chemical fertilizers (Bala, K., 2022).

Biofertilizer is an eco-friendly alternative to chemical fertilizer for a sustainable agriculture. The microbial inoculants help in growth directly or indirectly by fixing nitrogen (N), by solubilization of phosphorus (P) and potassium (K), by secreting siderophores, antibiotics, enzymes, antifungal, and antibacterial substances, and by releasing plant growth promoting hormones to enhance productivity and adaptability to overcome biotic and abiotic stresses. Many microorganism like Cyanobacteria, *Azotobacter*, *Azospirillum*, *Bacillus* sp., *Pseudomonas* sp., Actinomycetes, *Paenibacillus*, *Rhizobium*, arbuscular mycorrhiza fungi (AMF), and microalgae are applied in the preparation of biofertilizers.(Chakraborty, T. and Akhtar, N., 2021).

It offers an economically attractive and ecologically sound route for augmenting nutrient supply. Leguminous crops have the ability to fix nitrogen (N) biologically from the atmosphere. This can benefit not only the legumes themselves but also any intercropped or subsequent crops(Al Abboud, M.A *et al.*, 2014).

Biofertilizers are now a popular term among agriculturists. Many improvements have been done in existing techniques, and many new techniques had evolved as well to enhance its effects on plant system. It is being used extensively for biocontrol and plant growth promotion. Bioformulation is one of the areas of prime research importance as it affects the effectiveness of inoculants (Sahu, P.K *et al.*, 2018).

The Nutritional requirements of trees have received less attention compared to agricultural crops. Tree species provide a long-term investment for many potential benefits for human well-being. Nutritional supplementation is a requisite for improvement in the growth and quality of planting stock. Biofertilizers are a boon for chemical fertilizers, which produce several environmental hurdles. Being an alternate natural source of nutrients, biofertilizers help sustain soil health, fertility, and productivity while significantly improving the growth of plants. **(Jojoy, E.T. and Manohar K, A., 2024).**

Biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) refers to the process by which the nitrogen that is present abundantly in the atmosphere as non-reactive molecular dinitrogen (N_2) is converted into reactive forms that become available to plants and thereby to all life forms. The key process of BNF is the conversion of N_2 to ammonia (NH_3) catalyzed by the enzyme *nitrogenase*, which occurs in a group of microorganisms that exist in symbiotic association with certain plants especially legumes, or as free-living organisms **(Nair, P.R *et al.*, 2022)**

Azotobacter chroococcum spp. in crop production has manifested its significance in plant nutrition and its contribution to soil fertility. The possibility of using *Azotobacter chroococcum* in research experiments as microbial inoculant through production of growth substances and their effects on the plant has markedly enhanced crop production in agriculture. Being free living N_2 -fixer diazotroph, *Azotobacteria* genus synthesizes auxins, cytokinins, and GA like substances and these growth materials are the primary substances regulating the enhanced growth. **(Wani, S.A *et al.*, 2016).**

The biomass of the bacterium *Azotobacter chroococcum* can be used as a biofertilizer due to its ability to fix nitrogen from the atmosphere. In order to optimize the production of bacterial biomass for this purpose, a cultivation of *A. chroococcum* was done by using different media and cultivation techniques (batch, fed batch and repeated batch). Chemically defined and complex media with 20 g/l of sugar were selected as the most appropriate media for batch cultivation in stirred tank bioreactor. In order to obtain higher fed batch and repeated batch techniques were examined. **(Damir, O *et al.*, 2011).**

Cultures of *Azotobacter chroococcum* strain A6 were grown for 14 days in a nitrogen-deficient mineral medium, the supernatant fluid and bacteria extracted and examined by paper partition chromatography with two solvent systems which separate authentic

gibberellin (GA₃) and indolyl-3-acetic acid (IAA). (**Brown, M.E. and Burlingham, S.K., 1968**).

Nitrogen is an essential nutrient in plant growth. The ability of a plant to supply all or part of its requirements from biological nitrogen fixation (BNF) thanks to interactions with endosymbiotic, associative and endophytic symbionts, confers a great competitive advantage over non-nitrogen-fixing plants (**Santi, C *et al.*, 2013**).

Nitrogen is generally considered one of the major limiting nutrients in plant growth. The biological process responsible for reduction of molecular nitrogen into ammonia is referred to as nitrogen fixation. A wide diversity of nitrogen-fixing bacterial species belonging to most phyla of the Bacteria domain has the capacity to colonize the rhizosphere and to interact with plants. (**Bhat, T.A. *et al.*, 2015**).

A new generation of fertilizers made by coating granules with biopolymers address these issues. Coating in agriculture is an important area in research for a more sustainable future. Many examples and instances from existing research and related research gaps are discussed. It includes applications of composites as fertilizer's coating, advantages and disadvantages of fertilizer coating from composites, applications of bacteria in composite, applications of bacteria in fertilizer industry as well as the common techniques of coating fertilizers with drying process (**Tajarudin, H.A. and Ng, C.W.C., 2022**).

The formulated liquid biofertilizers of Rhizobium, Azotobacter, Azospirillum and PSB (*Bacillus megaterium*) were stored in BOD incubator at 28±2 °C for a period of 180 days and colony forming units were determined at monthly intervals. The liquid biofertilizers formulated using PVP in addition to glycerol at the rate of 0.5% each retained maximum number of colonies in all strains followed by PEG, GA and SA (**Santhosh, G.P., 2015**).

This technology harnesses the power of potential microbial strains and their cell-free filtrate possessing specific properties. The application of microbial bioformulations offers several remarkable advantages as a promising technology for the future of agriculture. To maintain the survival and viability of microbial strains, diverse carrier materials are employed to provide essential nourishment and support. Various carrier materials with their unique pros and cons are available, and choosing the most appropriate one is a key consideration, as it

substantially extends the shelf life of microbial cells and maintains the overall quality of the bioinoculants. (Khan, A *et al.*, 2023).

METHODOLOGY

Azotobacter chroococcum was isolated from rhizosphere soil collected from fertile agricultural fields using Ashby's Mannitol Agar, a nitrogen-free medium. The plates were incubated at 28–30 °C for 3–5 days, and characteristic large, gummy, opaque colonies were selected and maintained as pure cultures on Ashby's slants.

For mass multiplication, the pure culture was inoculated into a low-cost liquid medium prepared using jaggery, molasses, or cow dung slurry as carbon sources. The culture was grown in sterilized containers under aerated conditions, yielding a bacterial population of approximately 10^8 CFU/mL within 5–7 days.

The biofertilizer paint was formulated by preparing a natural paint base using slaked lime, casein, and glycerol, into which 30% (v/v) of the bacterial broth was aseptically mixed to obtain a brushable consistency. The prepared NitroGuard paint was applied to the lower trunk region (30–50 cm height) of selected trees such as mango, guava, and neem. Plant growth parameters including leaf greenness, shoot length, and leaf number were monitored and compared with untreated control trees.

RESULTS

Azotobacter chroococcum was successfully isolated from rhizosphere soil using Ashby's Mannitol Agar and mass multiplied using low-cost substrates such as jaggery, molasses, and cow dung slurry. The bacterial population reached approximately **10^8 CFU/mL within 5–7 days**.

A stable, water-based biofertilizer paint (NitroGuard) was formulated using slaked lime, casein, and glycerol. The paint showed good adhesion to tree bark and maintained microbial viability for **4–6 weeks** under ambient conditions.

Field application on selected trees resulted in **improved leaf greenness, increased shoot length, and better overall tree vigor** compared to untreated control trees. Viable *Azotobacter* cells were detected on the bark surface for up to **72 hours after application**, supporting successful establishment and movement toward the soil.

Table 1: Biochemical Test Results of *Azotobacter Chroococcum*.

TEST	RESULT
Glucose Fermentation	Positive
Sucrose	Positive
Indole	Negative
Methyl Red	Negative
Voges–Proskauer	Negative
Citrate utilization	Positive
Catalase	Positive
Starch hydrolysis	Positive
Urease	Positive
Gelatin hydrolysis	Positive

FIGURES

Figure 1: Isolation Of *Azotobacter Chroococcum*.

FIG 1.1 Ashbyi Mannitol Agar Medium.

FIG 1.2 Inoculation Of *A. chroococcum*.

Figure 2: Identification Of *Azotobacter chroococcum*

(A) Voges–Proskauer – Negative.

(B) Citrate – Positive.

Figure 3: Mass Multiplication Of *Azotobacter chroococcum*.

FIG 3.1: Inoculation of *A. chroococcum* in Ashbyi broth.

FIG 3.2: Mass Multiplication of *A. chroococcum*.

DISCUSSION AND SUMMARY

NitroGuard, a biofertilizer paint containing *Azotobacter chroococcum*, was successfully developed using low-cost, eco-friendly materials. The bacterium showed good viability when mass multiplied with farmer-friendly substrates and remained active in the paint formulation. Field application on tree trunks improved leaf greenness, shoot growth, and overall plant vigor compared to untreated controls. These effects are attributed to continuous biological nitrogen fixation and the production of plant growth-promoting substances by *Azotobacter*. The study confirms that biofertilizer paint is a feasible, sustainable alternative to chemical nitrogen fertilizers for tree crops.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

1. Sharma, D., Astapati, A.D., Dey, S., Bhattacharjee, D., Singha, D.M. and Nath, S., 2025. Microbial interactions in soil ecosystems: Facilitating plant growth, nutrient cycling, and environmental dynamics. In *Microbial Allies: Understanding Plant-Microbe Interactions in Sustainable Agriculture* (pp. 21-48). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
2. Monica, S., Panneerselvam, S., Rajasekaran, R., Nalliappan, S., Kailappan, A. and Rangasamy, A., 2025. Recent advances in bioinoculant formulations and their shelf-life: a review. *Current Microbiology*, 82(11): p.506.
3. Chakraborty, A.P., 2020. Carrier based bioformulations of PGPR-characteristics, shelf life and application in improving health status of crop plants—A mini review. *Int. J. Res. Rev.*, 7: pp.88-98.

4. Sethi, S.K. and Adhikary, S.P., 2012. Azotobacter: a plant growth-promoting rhizobacteria used as biofertilizer. *Dynamic Biochemistry, Process Biotechnology and Molecular Biology*, 6(1): pp.68-74.
5. Bala, K., 2022. Microbial fertilizer as an alternative to chemical fertilizer in modern agriculture. In *Beneficial microorganisms in agriculture* (pp. 111-130). Singapore: Springer Nature Singapore.
6. Chakraborty, T. and Akhtar, N., 2021. Biofertilizers: Characteristic features and applications. *Biofertilizers: Study and Impact*, pp.429-489.
7. Al Abboud, M.A., Ghany, T.A. and Alawlaqi, M.M., 2014. Role of biofertilizers in agriculture: a brief review. *Mycopath*, 11(2).
8. Sahu, P.K., Gupta, A., Singh, M., Mehrotra, P. and Brahma Prakash, G.P., 2018. Bioformulation and fluid bed drying: A new approach towards an improved biofertilizer formulation. In *Eco-friendly agro-biological techniques for enhancing crop productivity* (pp. 47-62). Singapore: Springer Singapore.
9. Jojy, E.T. and Manohar K, A., 2024. Strengthening Tree Nutrition Through the Application of Biofertilizers. In *Sustainable Plant Nutrition and Soil Carbon Sequestration* (pp. 267-284). Cham: Springer Nature Switzerland.
10. Nair, P.R., Kumar, B.M. and Nair, V.D., 2022. Biological nitrogen fixation and nitrogen fixing trees. In *An Introduction to Agroforestry: Four Decades of Scientific Developments* (pp. 413-443). Cham: Springer International Publishing.
11. Wani, S.A., Chand, S., Wani, M.A., Ramzan, M. and Hakeem, K.R., 2016. Azotobacterchroococcum—a potential biofertilizer in agriculture: an overview. *Soil science: agricultural and environmental perspectives*, pp.333-348.
12. Damir, O., Mladen, P., Božidar, S. and Srñan, N., 2011. Cultivation of the bacterium Azotobacterchroococcum for preparation of biofertilizers. *African Journal of Biotechnology*, 10(16): pp.3104-3111.
13. Brown, M.E. and Burlingham, S.K., 1968. Production of plant growth substances by Azotobacterchroococcum. *Microbiology*, 53(1): pp.135-144.
14. Santi, C., Bogusz, D. and Franche, C., 2013. Biological nitrogen fixation in non-legume plants. *Annals of botany*, 111(5): pp.743-767.
15. Bhat, T.A., Ahmad, L., Ganai, M.A. and Khan, O.A., 2015. Nitrogen fixing biofertilizers; mechanism and growth promotion: a review. *J Pure Appl Microbiol*, 9(2): pp.1675-1690.
16. Tajarudin, H.A. and Ng, C.W.C., 2022. *Biocoating for Fertilizer Industry*. Springer.

17. Santhosh, G.P., 2015. Formulation and shelf life of liquid biofertilizer inoculants using cell protectants. *Int J Res Biosci Agric Technol*, 7(2): pp.243-247.
18. Khan, A., Singh, A.V., Gautam, S.S., Agarwal, A., Punetha, A., Upadhayay, V.K., Kukreti, B., Bundela, V., Jugran, A.K. and Goel, R., 2023. Microbial bioformulation: a microbial assisted biostimulating fertilization technique for sustainable agriculture. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 14: p.1270039.